

TERASUN

Towards Terawatt Production of c-Si Solar Photovoltaics

D1.10 Data management plan and open science (DMP) M18

Funded by
the European Union

TERASUN project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No 101147545. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

General Information

Responsible	IDE
WP # and title	WP1 Team alignment and project management
Contributors	ALL partners
Dissemination level	PU
Type	Report
Due date	M18
Submission date	30.11.2025

Project Profile

Table 1 Key figures of the TERASUN project.

Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-11
Number	101147545
Acronym	TERASUN
Name	Towards Terawatt Production of c-Si Solar Photovoltaics
Start Date	1 June 2024
End Date	31 May 2027
Duration	36 months
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting authority	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Coordinator	IDENER

TERASUN Consortium Partners

Table 2 List of partners in the TERASUN project including acronym and country.

#	Partner	Short	CO
1	IDENER R&D AGRUPACION DE INTERES ECONOMICO	IDE	ES
2	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems	ISE	DE
3	PV2+	PV2+	DE
4	Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	CEA	FR
5	Technische Universiteit Delft	TUD	NL
6	RINA Consulting – Centro Sviluppo Materiali SPA	RINA-CSM	IT
7	Fyzikalni Ustav AV CR V.V.I	FZU	CZ

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Executive Summary

The present document's objective is to provide the TERASUN consortium with guidelines for data management and handling. It contains detailed information about the types of data generated during the project, standards for organisation and dissemination, verification and re-use, as well as procedures for managing and preserving data over time. This public document streamlines the process for external researchers interested in using or validating the project's datasets by facilitating their identification.

Aligned with the Horizon Europe guidelines, TERASUN adopts an open scientific approach, promoting a research culture of openness, accessibility, reusability, and interdisciplinary collaboration. The project prioritises societal benefits, aligning with **Horizon Europe's (HEU)** goals for ground-breaking research. The consortium upholds HEU's communication, dissemination, open science, and visibility policy, as outlined in Programme Regulations (Article 14 and 39) and the General Model Grant Agreement and aligns with the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

This document details datasets collected and used within the project for consortium partners and third parties. Data management involves categorising and technically describing data collection, processing, and creation within the TERASUN consortium.

The initial datasets were defined using a template based on FAIR principles, are provided in Annex I. This **second** iteration of the data management plan will be updated with new information in M36. In this version all the changes have been highlighted with **yellow marker**.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CINEA	EU Climate, Environment and Infrastructure Executive Agency
c-Si	Crystalline silicon
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DST	Decision Support Tool
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SHJ	Silicon Heterojunction
TCO	Transparent Conductive Oxide
Teams	Microsoft Teams
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
HEU	Horizon Europe

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the TERASUN project. The DMP details policies for handling, storing, and sharing project data throughout its lifecycle. It identifies data types, collection methods, processing, analysis, and storage procedures. The plan also covers data sharing and dissemination, considering Intellectual Property intentions.

TERASUN adopts the "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" principle, balancing Open Access benefits with the need to protect sensitive information. The DMP provides guidance on data formats, metadata, and management standards to ensure consistency and facilitate data sharing and reuse.

The present deliverable "*D1.3 Data management plan & open science (DMP) M6*" will be updated twice more, in D1.10 [M18] and D1.11 [M36], during the lifecycle of the TERASUN project.

1.2. Scope of this document

The DMP's primary goal is to ensure proper management of all data collected and generated during the TERASUN project. It aims to facilitate result replication and support further research.

Key objectives include:

1. Introducing data lifecycle and management best practices
2. Identifying data processed or generated within the project
3. Detailing data management, usage, storage, and treatment procedures
4. Addressing ethical aspects
5. Considering open-source approach implications

2. Data management

2.1. Data Life Cycle

The data life cycle is a systematic process for managing data throughout its lifespan. It encompasses collection, storage, processing, analysis, preservation, and sharing stages. This approach ensures secure, ethical, and efficient data handling during any project. Following the data life cycle promotes reproducibility, integrity, and potential reuse. Researchers can effectively leverage data to gain insights, meet objectives, and contribute to scientific knowledge. This iterative process, illustrated in Figure 1, involves continuous data management and refinement. The cycle's stages are described below.

Figure 1 Data life cycle throughout a project.

2.1.1. Data storage

Gathering

This initial stage involves collecting data from diverse sources. Methods include electronic capture, physical collection, and observation. This foundational step is the basis for any subsequent data processing and analysis activities.

Characterisation

After collection, data requires processing and organisation to ensure relevance and meaning for the research questions and objective(s). This stage involves cleaning, formatting, transforming, and labelling the data. Characterisation enhances data quality and structure, preparing it for effective analysis.

Analysis

Following characterisation, data analysis commences to generate insights or support research objectives. This stage may involve e.g. applying statistical techniques, machine learning algorithms, or other analytical methods to uncover patterns, trends, or relationships within the dataset.

Re-collection

During analysis, gaps in the dataset may become evident, necessitating additional data collection. The re-collection stage involves gathering supplementary information to refine the analysis or address specific research questions, thereby enhancing the overall findings.

2.1.2. Archive

This phase secures data for future access and compliance. It involves creating backups, implementing version control, and ensuring long-term storage. This process maintains and ensures data integrity, supports research reproducibility, and enables future data reuse.

2.1.3. Publication

In this phase research outcomes are shared with target audiences. It involves disseminating findings through academic papers, reports, presentations, and data repositories. This process facilitates knowledge sharing and enables other researchers to build upon the results.

2.1.4. Data re-use

This final phase utilises stored and published information for further research. It may involve sharing data with other researchers, adhering to ethical and legal guidelines. This process can spark new insights, foster collaborations, and explore novel research questions, advancing knowledge in various fields.

2.2. Status in TERASUN

Currently, TERASUN is in the data storage phase, as all the tasks in work packages (WP) 2-4 produce data from samples that are being characterised (T2.4, T3.6, T4.3). The data will be continuously gathered in T5.1 and the initial database version will launch in M12 (D5.4), with a final release in M36 (D5.6). The present deliverable lists and characterises expected datasets from TERASUN activities in the Data summary section.

2.3. Best practice

To manage data effectively throughout TERASUN's development, we must consider the EU's data management guide. This resource helps identify data generated by each consortium partner and establish clear handling rules. The following sections are crucial for ensuring all project members understand, align with and adhere to the data management processes. Proper data management requires fulfilling key criteria, including conventions for data identification, version management, and designated access locations. This structured approach promotes consistency and accessibility for all stakeholders.

Another topic is data security, which must be maintained throughout the project. Therefore, certain behaviours are discouraged to protect data integrity and confidentiality. The use of external memory devices, .e.g. USB sticks, is an example for potentially harmful behaviour. More detailed security measures are outlined below.

A primary goal is providing open access to the data generated throughout the project, involving depositing publications in repositories and ensuring open access. The EU offers guidelines for meeting requirements, which should be consulted when developing datasets or sharing files. By adhering to the EU's guide and implementing recommended practices, TERASUN can effectively manage its data assets, ensuring transparency, accessibility, and compliance with established standards.

2.4. Storing data and software

Microsoft SharePoint serves as a centralised digital repository for project files and documents. It enables consortium members to collaborate efficiently by creating, editing, and sharing files while ensure that the information is always up-to-date. Microsoft Teams (Teams) complements SharePoint by facilitating communication and meeting organisation. This combination ensures effective collaboration among members, regardless of their location.

Where appropriate, GitHub repositories will be established to efficiently manage the software development in the project, i.e. the development of the Terasun Decision Support Tool (DST) in WP5. This version control system enables effective code management and progress tracking. The team will adhere to the latest software development standards and recommendations. This approach ensures high-quality software that meets the highest standards.

The Terasun website <https://terasun.eu/> is publicly available and will be used to share information about the project such as results and publications.

2.5. Roles and responsibilities

As Terasun's coordinator, IDE will manage the Microsoft Teams group and SharePoint. Furthermore, IDE is also responsible for regularly updating the Data Management Plan (DMP) throughout the project (D1.10 [M18] and D1.11 [M36]). Relevant updates will be included in periodic reports, ensuring the DMP aligns with evolving data management requirements. IDE will keep the plan current, providing clear guidelines on personal data management and GDPR compliance. The DMP will outline project data management procedures and guide appropriate handling of all generated data. The consortium will inform IDE about project-managed data and highlight potential risks or considerations. With consortium support, IDE will ensure the final DMP version accurately reflects any updates to data management policies and practices identified during the project's lifecycle.

3. FAIR data

3.1. The definition of FAIR

FAIR data principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—aim to enhance data value and utility. These guidelines address challenges in data sharing and reuse across scientific research and other domains.

F	Findable data requires unique, persistent identifiers and comprehensive metadata. This approach enables researchers to easily search and locate relevant data using appropriate repositories or catalogues.
A	Accessible data should be openly available to humans and machines, respecting privacy and legal concerns. This involves removing access barriers, providing clear instructions, and using open standards to facilitate seamless access.
I	Interoperable data is structured for integration with diverse sources. It employs standardised vocabularies, ontologies, and data models for easy interpretation and exchange. Open formats and APIs further enhance interoperability across different systems and platforms.
R	Reusable data is well-documented, includes details about its origin, context, and usage rights. Clear, standardised terms and licences encourage effective reuse and citation, promoting collaboration and reproducibility in research.

FAIR data principles foster data sharing, collaboration, and research reproducibility. They maximise data's impact and reuse potential, enabling effective integration into new investigations. The European Commission encourages FAIR research data to enhance the integrity and impact of their research investments.

3.2. FAIR data in TERASUN

The TERASUN Consortium will carefully assess each situation and strike a balance between openness, information preservation, commercialisation, and intellectual property rights, while addressing privacy and security concerns. The project will ensure data confidentiality, accessibility, and result validation, adhering to appropriate intellectual property governance and partner agreements.

Decision-making procedures will be implemented to maximise open access to research outcomes without compromising commercial interests. Figure 2 illustrates the dissemination/exploitation decision process, while Figure 3 outlines preliminary results and their expected dissemination/exploitation pathways.

The TERASUN Consortium will present research outcomes accessibly, understandably, and in an exchangeable and reusable manner whilst ensuring data security and result validation. Partners will

therefore aspire to make non-sensitive data available as green or gold open-access publications (e.g. journal articles, magazines etc.).

Figure 2 Decision-making tree for the dissemination or exploitation of new datasets.

TERASUN will meet funding and regulatory requirements, maintaining data accuracy and authenticity. A common data management structure will be applied across all WPs, particularly for WP2-5. This structure will clarify:

- Outputs of each WP
- Data requirements for processes
- Logistics responsibilities

The DMP will be continuously revised, describing generated research data and applicable policies. Funding and legal policies for data management will be determined. Raw and generated data will be uploaded to an open repository, contributing to HEU's open access approach to scientific data. For the case that personal data is to be used to reach the project's objectives, the EU Commission will be informed to ensure compliance with HEU ethics regulations, [GDPR](#), and local regulations.

4. Data summary

This section outlines data generated and collected by partners during TERASUN. Categorising data using FAIR principles is crucial for an effective DMP. IDE created a template to identify primary datasets for each WP (Table 4). Detailed characteristics are reported in Annex I. Additional information will be included as it becomes available.

To facilitate data tracking, the datasets (DS) use the nomenclature:

TERASUN_DS_WP#_PARTNER_Title

The initial DMP version lists identified datasets, fully characterised using the template shown in Table 4 and reported in Annex I.

Table 3: Data sources in the TERASUN project.

Source	Description
Management	Data related to management tasks, collected in WP1.
Observational	Data gathered in real-time e.g. through operators' feedback or sensor readings (WP2-4). Data collected from stakeholders (WP6).
Experimental	Data gathered from characterisation of samples (e.g. crystalline silicon [c-Si] wafers, glass, photovoltaic cells or modules etc.).
Simulation	Data generated by optical models for the activities in WP2.
Derived	Data from reproducible experimental datasets as inputs for modelling (WP2), environmental and economic, and replicability (WP5).
References / canonical	Standardised, high-quality data e.g. from databases used for modelling (WP2), sustainability assessment (WP5), and dissemination, communication and exploitation activities (WP6).

4.1. Initial datasets and dataset template

A list of datasets, initially identified by the TERASUN consortium, is provided in Annex I. Additional datasets might be added to the list in the updates of this DMP (D1.10 [M18] and D1.11 [M36]).

The template in Table 4 was provided to the entire TERASUN consortium to collect information about the different datasets that will be relevant for the project. The filled templates are regrouped in Annex I for clarity.

Table 4: TERASUN Datasets FAIR characterisation template

TERASUN_DS_WPX_PARTNER_Title		
Dataset Title	[Data Title]	
Type of Data	[Classification] e.g. Management / Observational / Experimental / Simulation / Derived / Reference-canonical (Table 3)	
Short description	[Description] e.g. the database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	[Acronym], e.g. IDE	
WP – Task	[WP# – Task #.#], e.g. WP1 – T1.1	
Expected period	[Start month- End month], e.g. M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	[Explanation]	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: e.g. This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.'). word file (.doc, python file .py, images jpg; or videos mp4)</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: e.g. Partner short name - Country - Name and surname - Position in the organisation - Email - Phone number - Skype ID - Teams user - Role within the project</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP#_PARTNER_Title_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: date in format YYYY/MM/DD</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Will the data be publicly accessible? If so, what methods will be used for sharing?</p> <p>How will it be accessible? Any methods or software tools need for the access?</p> <p>Restrictions: e.g. this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): e.g. the contact list contains personal information.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: e.g. the text file's structure will promote flexibility and compatibility across project data. Industry standards will be prioritised where feasible to enhance interoperability and ease of use.</p>
	Reusability	<p>Can the data be reused? Are licenses required? Duration of the reusability?</p> <p>Example: Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft</p>

	Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders.
Other comments	[Comments]

5. Data security

The responsibility of maintaining data security lies with each organisation's IT specialists who will manage digital assets. All the partners will implement security measures aligned with company policies to maintain data integrity. IDE, owning Terasun's shared platforms (Microsoft Teams and SharePoint), will secure data and restrict access to authorised users only.

The Terasun consortium will follow specific processes, including multi-location storage (at least two) and systematic file labelling, to prevent data loss and ensure easy tracking. The use of flash drives shall be limited. These measures will maximise the security and integrity of Terasun's digital assets and resources, mitigating risks of data loss and unauthorised access throughout the project's lifecycle.

6. Open-source considerations

An open-source approach utilises freely accessible software tools and methodologies. It allows anyone to view, modify, and distribute the source code under specific licences. This method fosters collaboration, transparency, and adaptability in software development. The advantages of this approach are the following: **(1) cost-effectiveness**: a large percentage of open-source software is available free-of-charge or at significantly lower cost than proprietary software, making it the obvious choice for researchers and institutions; **(2) flexibility**: due to direct access to the code, open-source software can be adapted to specific needs and workflows; **(3) transparency**: direct access to the code also ensures that the software is trustworthy and reliable as it can be reviewed by a broad range of users; **(4) collaboration**: open-source software fosters a culture of collaboration among researchers and promotes knowledge- and data-sharing.

Open-source data management planning utilises free software tools for creating, managing, and sharing research data. These platforms offer storage, sharing, and version control features, enhancing data organisation and efficiency. This approach also adheres to open standards and best practices, like FAIR principles, which promote data accessibility and reusability. By following these guidelines, researchers can improve data discoverability and shareability. Ultimately, open-source data management planning fosters collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and more effective data management within the research community.

6.1. TERASUN DST

Following the aim to provide a reliable basis for decision-making with the TERASUN DST (developed in WP5), selected content will be shared via the project's dissemination and communication channels (WP6). This way a wide public of policymakers and industrial stakeholders will be reached. The dissemination, communication and exploitation activities in WP6 will include publications, deliverables, leaflets, brochures etc., but also the definition of key exploitable results to engage stakeholders.

6.2. Free-of-charge EU platforms for dissemination and exploitation

Several platforms are provided by the European Commission¹, offering free-of-charge services for dissemination and exploitation activities in EU-funded projects.

[Open Research Europe](#): To publish scientific papers for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including open peer review and article revision.

[Horizon Results Platform](#): To showcase project research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others. The [TV section](#) includes also testimonials and interviews from project participants that have succeeded as entrepreneurs.

[Horizon Results Booster](#): For consulting including portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.

[Horizon Standardisation Booster](#): Support service to increase and valorise project results through standardisation.

[Innovation Radar](#): Initiative to strengthen connections between EU-funded innovators, European investors, and policymakers in member states to help high-potential innovations to reach the market.

6.3. Open access repository

Open Access Repositories like PubMed, Zenodo, and arXiv can be found using platforms such as ROAR, OpenDOAR, OpenAIRE, and OAD. Zenodo, is a portal supported by the EU which uses GIT version control and Digital Object Identifier (DOI) systems. Zenodo offers free repository services for sharing research data and outputs and preserves digital data through backups and replication, assigning unique DOIs for traceability. The TERASUN consortium will primarily use e.g. Zenodo for long-term data preservation, managed by IDE who oversees data management.

¹ [European Research Executive Agency, Dissemination and exploitation](#), website [accessed September 2024]]

6.4. Open publications

All peer-reviewed scientific publications from Horizon Europe funding must be made open access. This requires immediate, free online availability without usage restrictions, deposited in a repository. Open access for peer-reviewed publications is mandatory in Horizon Europe, with immediate publication under open licenses (e.g., Creative Commons), providing specific minimum reuse rights (CC BY or similar).

To maximise impact and cost-effectiveness, the researchers engaged in TERASUN will use the two following strategies: **Green Open Access** or **Gold Open Access** (see boxes on the right²) In TERASUN the Gold Open Access will be used when publishers do not accept the Green Open Access model without embargo periods. Publications with embargo periods prior to publications, do not comply with Horizon Europe regulations.

EC tools like Open Research Europe can enhance diffusion and exploitation efforts. This platform helps beneficiaries comply with open access terms and facilitates rapid result sharing.

A list of potential scientific journals and conferences is provided in the PEDR (D6.3 [M6]) as support material.

Open access will make the TERASUN project more impactful by:

- Improving research speed, efficiency, effectiveness, reproducibility, and collaborations.
- Increasing visibility, usage, and impact by benefiting professional, practitioner, business, and public communities.
- Receiving more citations than average for articles.

Green Open Access

Refers to self-archiving which involves uploading a publication to an online repository before, during, or after its official release. This process may include a temporary delay in access, known as an embargo period.

Gold Open Access

Open access publishing involves immediate availability through the publisher upon release. Publishers typically charge an open access fee to compensate for lost subscription revenue.

² European Research Council, website, [FAQ](#) search term “green open access” [accesses September 2024]

7. Ethical aspects

7.1. General data protection regulations

TERASUN project adheres to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Regulation (EU) 2016/679,³ applicable to EU member countries since May 25th, 2018⁴. The project follows GDPR guidelines to protect all collected, processed, and stored data.

According to Article 4 of the GDPR personal data is defined as information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, the data subject. Identification of the data subject can happen directly or indirectly. This may occur through various identifiers, including names, ID numbers, location data, or online identifiers. Additionally, identification can be made through specific physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social factors.

Furthermore, Article 4 defines processing as any operation performed on personal data, automated or not. These operations include the collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction. TERASUN ensures GDPR compliance in all data processing actions, especially concerning personal data or imagery.

Norm-critical stakeholder engagement and societal impact analysis (T#.# etc.) will consider sub-group needs and attitudes. During the TERASUN project data on protected traits will be gathered to ensure diverse representation. Information will be aggregated to maintain anonymity and all data processes will adhere to GDPR regulations.

As partner in charge of dissemination and communication activities (WP6), IDE has prepared a GDPR-compliant consent form for consortium partners and external participants (Annex II). This form has been filled and signed by most of the partners participating in TERASUN and it will be provided to external partners, participating in workshops. It gathers consent for sharing names, affiliations, pictures, and videos in communications activities and internal project management.

7.2. Considerations on artificial intelligence

The TERASUN consortium adheres to the EC guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research⁵.

7.2.1. *Development of secure, robust and trustworthy AI*

The European Commission's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) emphasise its proper use, especially given its rapid growth. The AI's trustworthiness hinges on *lawfulness* (compliance

³ [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#).

⁴ [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR), website [accessed September 2024].

⁵ Living guidelines on the RESPONSIBLE USE OF GENERATIVE AI IN RESEARCH, First Version March 2024 ([PDF](#)).

with all applicable laws and regulations), *ethics* (adhering to ethical principles and values), and *robustness* (from a technical and social point of view).

TERASUN prioritises these pillars, applying a human-centric approach to AI development. The project includes initiatives like Terasun DST integration (WP5), potentially involving AI-based multidisciplinary design optimization and smart digital tools. Users will be informed about AI system operations and potential automated actions.

7.2.2. Generative AI usage in Terasun

Concerning the use of generative AI in the preparation of reports and deliverables, the Terasun consortium ensures the text's accuracy, validity, and suitability. The output of generative AI tools are merely used as compositional aids for composing the final text, acknowledging AI's limitations like biases, errors, and knowledge gaps. The consortium explicitly avoids plagiarism by primarily using these tools to refine existing content rather than generating new material.

Annex I: TERASUN datasets

IDE datasets

TERASUN_DS_WP1_IDE_Contacts		
Dataset Title	Project contact list	
Type of Data	Management	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	IDE	
WP – Task	WP1 – Team alignment and project management	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	Facilitate the communication between the partners and ensure the efficient execution of TERASUN project.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet ('.xlsx').</p> <p>Location: TERASUN SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: partner ID, partner short name, country, organisation type, contact person (name and surname), information about the GDPR consent form (signed or not), role in the project, email address, involvement in WPs, phone number and address of the organisation.</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP1_IDE_Contacts</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available.</p> <p>Restrictions: The dataset is not public and available only to beneficiaries through project's SharePoint.</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the contact list contains personal information.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: does not apply
	Reusability	This dataset can be accessed and used by partners by logging in the TERASUN Teams group and accessing the SharePoint. It will be updated along the project duration.
Data security	The project's internally collected data is not intended for long-term storage. Personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Throughout the project, data security measures outlined in the Data Management Plan will be implemented.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	

Other comments	N/A
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TERASUN_DS_WP1_IDE_Minutes		
Dataset Title	Project meeting minutes	
Type of Data	Management	
Short description	The meeting minutes created throughout the project contain details on the execution of the different tasks and their status.	
Responsible partner	IDE	
WP – Task	WP1 – Team alignment and project management	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	Facilitate the communication between the partners and ensure the efficient execution of TERASUN project.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This data is stored as in text ('.docx', '.pdf') or presentation ('.pptx').</p> <p>Location: TERASUN SharePoint folder or shared via email.</p> <p>Containing fields: attendants, date, summary of the points discussed during the meetings, conclusion and next steps.</p> <p>Name convention followed: YYYYMMDD_TERASUN_MeetingTitle_Minutes</p> <p>Version numbering: date in format YY/MM/DD</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available.</p> <p>Restrictions: The dataset is not public and available only to beneficiaries through project's SharePoint or email.</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the minutes may contain confidential information.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: does not apply
	Reusability	This dataset can be accessed and used by partners by logging in the TERASUN Teams group and accessing the SharePoint. It can be accessed during a specified period after the meeting for updates, and anytime for checking the points discussed during the meeting and its conclusions.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP1_IDE_Overview		
Dataset Title	Project overview	
Type of Data	Management	
Short description	The database contains technical and organisational details.	
Responsible partner	IDE	
WP – Task	WP1 – Team alignment and project management	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	Facilitate the communication between the partners and ensure the efficient execution of TERASUN project.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet ('.xlsx').</p> <p>Location: TERASUN SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: Wafers (sizes), Glass (sizes), Devices (sizes), Characterisation (partner, tool, comments, automatic, for cells and modules, wafer sizes), TCOs (partner, TCO type, description, comments), Exchange (sending partner, receiving partner, experiment name, description, shipping date, reception date, comments), Maintenance & Vacation (partner, start and end dates), Consortium and Review Meetings (partner, meeting type, name of event, month, start and end date, location, SharePoint link, comments), Deliverables (WP, DV ID, DV number, name, description, lead, type, dissemination level, due date, due month), Milestones (number, names, WP, partner, means of verification, due date, due month), Publications (partner, type, title, 1st author, pub. date, journal, pages, volume, issue, DOI, comments), and Dissemination material (partner, dissemination type, event, title, presenter, dates, location, website, SharePoint link).</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP1_IDE_Contacts</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available.</p> <p>Restrictions: The dataset is not public and available only to beneficiaries through project's SharePoint.</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the contact list contains personal information.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: does not apply
	Reusability	This dataset can be accessed and used by partners by logging in the TERASUN Teams group and accessing the SharePoint. It will be updated along the project duration.
Data security	The project's internally collected data is not intended for long-term storage. Personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Throughout the project, data security measures outlined in the Data Management Plan will be implemented.	

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

ISE datasets⁶

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_ELLIPSO		
Dataset Title	ISE_ELLIPSO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of ellipsometer at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date , layer thickness and associated model	
Responsible partner	ISE	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the thickness and optical properties (n&k) of layers of TCO layers developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP3)	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Thickness, n&k, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_ELLIPSO_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	

⁶ Note that PV2+ uses the same laboratories and equipment as ISE, therefore no additional list of datasets was added for this partner.

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_REFLECTO		
Dataset Title	ISE_REFLECTO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	ISE	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, reflectance value at different wavelength, effective reflectance, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_reflectance_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project	

	duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_SPECTRO

Dataset Title	ISE_SPECTRO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance, transmittance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	ISE	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, reflectance and transmittance value at different wavelength, effective reflectance/transmittance, absorption, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_spectro_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_4PP		
Dataset Title	ISE_4PP	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance, transmittance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	ISE	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the sheet resistance of layers and the electrical properties of layers in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Rsheet, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_4PP_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams

		platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_HALL		
	Dataset Title	ISE_HALL
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the results of Hall effect at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the opto-electric properties of layers such as electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity for developed layers in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP3)
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity, conductivity Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_HALL_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams

		platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_SINTON-WCT		
Dataset Title		ISE_SINTON_WCT
Type of Data		Experimental
Short description		The database contains the results of Sinton WCT (lifetime measurement at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, lifetime, resistivity, iVoc, iFF
Responsible partner		ISE
WP – Task		WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period		M4-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To determine the passivation properties of layers such as effective minor carrier lifetime, implied Voc for developed layers and devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2, 3, 4)
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, Tau-eff @E15 ; iVoc at 1sun resistivity, iVoc, IFF Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_Sinton-WCT_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.

Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_SUNS-VOC		
Dataset Title	ISE_SUNS-VOC	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of SunsVoc at ISE partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, pFF.	
Responsible partner	ISE	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the potential external PV parameters of cells (without series resistance effect).for developed devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP4)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, pseudo (p)FF, p Efficiency, pVoc Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_SUNS-VOC_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams

		platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_OPT-MICROSCOPE		
Dataset Title		ISE_OPT-MICROSCOPE
Type of Data		Experimental
Short description		The database contains the results of morphology analysis (images): for textured wafers : pyramid counts on different points, pyramid size for metallisation wafers : line width
Responsible partner		ISE
WP – Task		WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period		M4-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To observe and analyse the morphology surface : pyramid counts on different points, pyramid size for textured wafers and line width (for metallisation) for developed devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP4)
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_OPT-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.

Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE	
Dataset Title	ISE_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains the results of morphology analysis (images)
Responsible partner	ISE
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period	M4-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To observe and analyse the surface morphology
F A I R	Findability <i>Format:</i> This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images <i>Location:</i> SharePoint folder <i>Containing fields:</i> no further details available at this point <i>Name convention followed:</i> TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD <i>Version numbering:</i> not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility <i>Access:</i> Not openly available, publication possible <i>Restrictions:</i> this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). <i>Justification of restriction (if so):</i> the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability <i>Data exchange and reuse ease:</i> The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.

Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_SEM+EDX	
Dataset Title	ISE_SEM+EDX
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains the images of the surface and cross section morphology and the results of chemical composition of layers
Responsible partner	ISE
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period	M4-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To examine the surface and cross section morphology and chemical composition of layers
F A I R	Findability <i>Format:</i> This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images <i>Location:</i> SharePoint folder <i>Containing fields:</i> no further details available at this point <i>Name convention followed:</i> TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_SEM+EDX_YYYYMMDD <i>Version numbering:</i> not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility <i>Access:</i> Not openly available, publication possible <i>Restrictions:</i> this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). <i>Justification of restriction (if so):</i> the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability <i>Data exchange and reuse ease:</i>

		The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_TLM		
	Dataset Title	ISE_TLM
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the data of the contact resistivity, Rsheet, R TLM
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the contact resistivity for the layers and devices developed on TERASUN project ; Contact between TCO layers and metallisation
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list (no further details available at this point) layer types, sample name, date, R contact, Rsheet, R TLM, distance inter lines Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_TLM_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities

	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_FWIS		
	Dataset Title	ISE_FWIS
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the data of wafer thickness, wafer resistivity, reflectivity, carrier lifetime and photoluminescence signal
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine of wafer thickness, wafer resistivity, reflectivity, carrier lifetime and photoluminescence signal of (semi-fabricated) devices
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list (no further details available at this point) sample name, date, wafer thickness, wafer resistivity, reflectivity, carrier lifetime and photoluminescence signal Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_FWIS_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities

	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_MODULUM-PL

	Dataset Title	ISE_MODULUM-PL
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the images of the PL of precursor cells a (after Passivation, after TCO) and PL of cells and value of PL mean
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To detect the defect areas on precursor cells and on cells. Allow to check also the Q-Time and contamination.
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list (no further details available at this point) sample name, date, photoluminescence signal, carrier lifetime (injection dependent) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_MODULUM-PL_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).

		<i>Justification of restriction (if so):</i> the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	<i>Data exchange and reuse ease:</i> The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_AWIS		
	Dataset Title	ISE_AWIS
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the measurements of as cut wafer on the inline inspection
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure the properties of as cut wafers : TTR , resistivity, size on M2
F A I R	Findability	<i>Format:</i> This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') <i>Location:</i> SharePoint folder <i>Containing fields:</i> : non exhaustive list (no further details available at this point) sample name, date, wafer thickness, wafer resistivity, wafer edge length <i>Name convention followed:</i> TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_AWIS_YYYYMMDD <i>Version numbering:</i> not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	<i>Access:</i> Not openly available, publication possible <i>Restrictions:</i> this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).

		Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_CALLAB		
	Dataset Title	ISE_CALLAB
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the measurements of solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin (for M2)
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure and determine the solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: cell name, partner, date, busbar number, cell size, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc (non-exhaustive list) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_CALLAB_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).

		Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_ISE_CELL-TESTER		
	Dataset Title	ISE_CELL-TESTER
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the measurements of solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin (for M2)
	Responsible partner	ISE
	WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure and determine the solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: cell name, partner, date, busbar number, cell size, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc (non-exhaustive list) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_ISE_CELL-TESTER_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible

	<p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
Reusability	<p>Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.</p>
Data security	<p>The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.</p>
Ethical aspects	<p>Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)</p>
Other comments	N/A

CEA datasets

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_ELLIPSO		
Dataset Title	CEA_ELLIPSO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of ellipsometer at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date , layer thickness and associated model	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the thickness and optical properties (n&k) of layers of TCO layers developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP3)	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Thickness, n&k, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_ELLIPSO_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_REFLECTO		
Dataset Title	CEA_REFLECTO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, reflectance value at different wavelength, effective reflectance, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_reflectance_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	

Other comments	N/A
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TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_SPECTRO		
Dataset Title	CEA_SPECTRO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance, transmittance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices developed in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, reflectance and transmittance value at different wavelength, effective reflectance/transmittance, absorption, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_spectro_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_4PP		
Dataset Title	CEA_4PP	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of reflectometer at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, reflectance, transmittance at different wavelength	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the sheet resistance of layers and the electrical properties of layers in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2 and 3)	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Rsheet, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_4PP_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_HALL		
Dataset Title	CEA_HALL	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of Hall effect at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the opto-electric properties of layers such as electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity for developed layers in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP3)	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity, conductivity Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_HALL_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_SINTON-WCT		
Dataset Title	CEA_SINTON_WCT	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of Sinton WCT (lifetime measurement at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, lifetime, resistivity, iVoc, iFF	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the passivation properties of layers such as effective minor carrier lifetime, implied Voc for developed layers and devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP2, 3, 4)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, Tau-eff @E15 ; iVoc at 1sun resistivity, iVoc, IFF Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_Sinton-WCT_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project	

	duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_SUNSVOC		
Dataset Title	CEA_SUNSVOC	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of SunsVoc at CEA partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, pFF.	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the potential external PV parameters of cells (without series resistance effect).for developed devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP4)	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, pseudo (p)FF, p Efficiency, pVoc Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_SunsVoc_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	

Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_OPT-MICROSCOPE		
Dataset Title	CEA_OPT-MICROSCOPE	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of morphology analysis (images): for textured wafers : pyramid counts on different points, pyramid size for metallisation wafers : line width	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To observe and analyse the morphology surface : pyramid counts on different points, pyramid size for textured wafers and line width (for metallisation) for developed devices in TERASUN and for the round robin (WP4)	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_OPT-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project	

	duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE		
Dataset Title	CEA_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of morphology analysis (images)	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To observe and analyse the surface morphology	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project	

	duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_SEM+EDX		
Dataset Title	CEA_SEM+EDX	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the images of the surface and cross section morphology and the results of chemical composition of layers	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To examine the surface and cross section morphology and chemical composition of layers	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_SEM+EDX_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_R-CONTACT		
Dataset Title	CEA_R-CONTACT	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the data of the contact resistivity	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the contact resistivity	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: Layer types, sample name, date, R contact Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_R-CONTACT_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_TLM		
Dataset Title	CEA_TLM	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the data of the contact resistivity, Rsheet, R TLM	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the contact resistivity for the layers and devices developed on TERASUN project ; Contact between TCO layers and metallisation	
FAIR	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list (no further details available at this point) layer types, sample name, date, R contact, Rsheet, R TLM, distance inter lines Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_TLM_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_EQE		
Dataset Title	CEA_EQE	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the data of external quantum efficiency and spectral response of cell	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure external quantum efficiency for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of CEA, for the round robin	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_EQE_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_PL		
Dataset Title	CEA_PL	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the images of the PL of precursor cells a (after Passivation, after TCO) and PL of cells and value of PL mean	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To detect the defect areas on precursor cells and on cells. Allow to check also the Q-Time and contamination.	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_PL_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams

		platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_XRD		
	Dataset Title	CEA_XRD
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the phase and structure
	Responsible partner	CEA
	WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure the properties of as cut wafers : TTR , resistivity, size on M2
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx')</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_XRD_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project

	duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_WIS		
Dataset Title	CEA_WIS	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the measurements of as cut wafer on the inline inspection	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure the properties of as cut wafers : TTR, size, resistivity on M2 wafers	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: no further details available at this point Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_WIS_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_CELL-TESTER_15BB		
Dataset Title	CEA_CELL-TESTER-15BB	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the measurements of solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure and determine the solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: cell name, partner, date, busbar number, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc (non-exhaustive list) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_CELL-TESTER-15BB_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams

		platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_CELL-TESTER_15BB		
	Dataset Title	CEA_CELL-TESTER-15BB
	Type of Data	Experimental
	Short description	The database contains the measurements of solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin (for M2, ½ G12 and G12 cells)
	Responsible partner	CEA
	WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
	Expected period	M4-M36
	Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure and determine the solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: cell name, partner, date, busbar number, cell size, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc (non-exhaustive list) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_CELL-TESTER-15BB_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.

Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_CEA_CELL-TESTER		
Dataset Title	CEA_CELL-TESTER	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the measurements of solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin (for M2)	
Responsible partner	CEA	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure and determine the solar cell characteristics: efficiency, Jsc, FF, Voc for the devices developed on TERASUN project , for reference cell of partners, for the round robin	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: cell name, partner, date, busbar number, cell size, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc (non-exhaustive list) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_CEA_CELL-TESTER_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease:

		The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
	Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.
	Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
	Other comments	N/A

TUD datasets

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_SPECTRO		
Dataset Title	TUD_SPECTRO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	TUD	
WP – Task	<p>WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures (T2.1 & 2.4 and other tasks if necessary)</p> <p>WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (if needed)</p> <p>WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (if needed)</p>	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list</p> <p>Layer types, sample name, date, reflectance and transmittance value at different wavelength, absorption, methodology (using standard samples)</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_SPECTRO_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_REFLECTO		
Dataset Title	TUD_REFLECTO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	TUD	
WP – Task	<p>WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures (T2.1 & 2.4 and other tasks if necessary)</p> <p>WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (if needed)</p> <p>WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (if needed)</p>	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the optical properties of layers and devices.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list</p> <p>Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, reflectance value at different wavelength, methodology (using standard samples)</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_REFLECTO_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP3-4_TUD_ELLIPSO		
Dataset Title	TUD_ELLIPSO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	TUD	
WP – Task	WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (T3.3 and other tasks if necessary) WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the thickness and optical properties (n&k) of layers	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls'). Location: SharePoint folder Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, Thickness, n&k, number of points, methodology (using standard samples) Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP3-4_TUD_ELLIPSO_YYYYMMDD Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available, publication possible . Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP3_TUD_4PP		
Dataset Title	TUD_4PP	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	TUD	
WP – Task	WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (T3.3 and other tasks if necessary)	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the sheet resistance of layers	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Rsheet, number of points, methodology (using standard samples)</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP3_TUD_4PP_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP3_TUD_HALL	
Dataset Title	TUD_HALL

Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.	
Responsible partner	TUD	
WP – Task	WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (T3.3 and other tasks if necessary)	
Expected period	M1-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the opto-electric properties of layers such as electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity.	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity, conductivity</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP3_TUD_HALL_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP3-4_TUD_SINTON-WCT

Dataset Title	TUD_SINTON-WCT
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.

Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (T3.5 and other tasks if necessary) WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)
Expected period	M1-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the passivation properties of layers such as effective minor carrier lifetime, implied Voc.
F A I R	Findability <i>Format:</i> This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.'). <i>Location:</i> SharePoint folder <i>Containing fields:</i> non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, Tau-eff @E15 ; iVoc at 1sun resistivity, iVoc, IFF <i>Name convention followed:</i> TERASUN_DS_WP3-4_TUD_SINTON-WCT_YYYYMMDD <i>Version numbering:</i> not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility <i>Access:</i> Not openly available, publication possible . <i>Restrictions:</i> This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). <i>Justification of restriction (if so):</i> Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability <i>Data exchange and reuse ease:</i> The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_SUNS-VOC	
Dataset Title	TUD_SUNS-VOC
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)

Expected period	M1-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the potential external PV parameters of cells (without series resistance effect).
FAIR	Findability <i>Format:</i> This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.'). <i>Location:</i> SharePoint folder <i>Containing fields:</i> non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, pseudo (p)FF, p Efficiency, pVoc <i>Name convention followed:</i> TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_SUNS-VOC_YYYYMMDD <i>Version numbering:</i> not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking
	Accessibility <i>Access:</i> Not openly available, publication possible. <i>Restrictions:</i> This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams). <i>Justification of restriction (if so):</i> Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability <i>Data exchange and reuse ease:</i> The data and methodologies will be exchanged and reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 4 and 5.
Data security	Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects	Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments	N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_OPT-MICROSCOPE	
Dataset Title	TUD_OPT-MICROSCOPE
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures (if needed) WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (if needed) WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (if needed)
Expected period	M1-M36

Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To examine the surface morphology.
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images.</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_OPT-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_SEM+EDX	
Dataset Title	TUD_SEM+EDX
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	<p>WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures (T2.1 & 2.4 and other tasks if necessary)</p> <p>WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (if needed)</p> <p>WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (if needed)</p>
Expected period	M1-M36

Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To examine the surface and cross section morphology and chemical composition of layers.
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images.</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_SEM+EDX_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE	
Dataset Title	TUD_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	<p>WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures (if needed)</p> <p>WP3 – In-free TCOs, Ag-free metallisation, passivation, and novel passivating contacts (if needed)</p> <p>WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (if needed)</p>
Expected period	M1-M36

Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To examine the surface morphology.
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images.</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_TUD_CONFOCAL-MICROSCOPE_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security		Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects		Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_TLM	
Dataset Title	TUD_TLM
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.1 and 4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)
Expected period	M1-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the contact resistivity.

F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list layer types, sample name, date, R contact, Rsheet, R TLM, distance inter lines</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_TLM_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	<p>Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 4 and 5.</p>
Data security	<p>Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.</p>	
Ethical aspects	<p>Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)</p>	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_CELL-TESTER	
Dataset Title	TUD_CELL-TESTER
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.1 and 4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)
Expected period	M1-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the external PV parameters.

F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non-exhaustive list cell name, partner, date, cell size, Efficiency, Jsc, FF and Voc</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_CELL-TESTER_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	<p>Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 4 and 5.</p>
Data security	<p>Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.</p>	
Ethical aspects	<p>Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)</p>	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_EQE	
Dataset Title	TUD_EQE
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains name, organisation, and contact details for all project partners.
Responsible partner	TUD
WP – Task	WP4 – Photovoltaic cells and modules (T4.1.1 and 4.1.4 and other tasks if necessary)
Expected period	M1-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure external quantum efficiency.

F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xls.').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP4_TUD_EQE_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible.</p> <p>Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities.</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease: The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	<p>Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 4 and 5.</p>
	Data security	<p>Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.</p>
	Ethical aspects	<p>Applicable international, EU and national law in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament: General Data Protection Regulation)</p>
	Other comments	N/A

RINA-CSM datasets

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_RINA-CSM_HALL		
Dataset Title	RINA-CSM_HALL	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of Hall effect at RINA-CSM partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity	
Responsible partner	RINA-CSM	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the opto-electric properties of layers such as electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity for developed layers in TERASUN (WP3)	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, electron mobility, carrier density, resistivity, conductivity</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_RINA-CSM_HALL_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_RINA-CSM_SEM+EDX		
Dataset Title	RINA-CSM_SEM+EDS	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the images of the surface and cross section morphology and the results of chemical composition of layers	
Responsible partner	RINA-CSM	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To examine the surface and cross section morphology and chemical composition of layers	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_RINA-CSM_SEM+EDX_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_RINA-CSM-CSM_SEM+EDX		
Dataset Title	RINA-CSM_TEM	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the images of the surface and cross section morphology and the results of chemical composition of layers	
Responsible partner	RINA-CSM	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To produce high-resolution, nanoscale images that reveal both surface and internal structures of layer	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx') for analysis and in dedicated folder for images</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_RINA-CSM_TEM_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_RINA-CSM_XRD		
Dataset Title	RINA-CSM_XRD	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the phase and structure	
Responsible partner	RINA-CSM	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To measure the properties of as cut wafers : TTR , resistivity, size on M2	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx')</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: no further details available at this point</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_RINA-CSM_XRD_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders	
Other comments	N/A	

TERASUN_DS_TERASUN_DS_WP2-4_RINA-CSM_ELLIPSO		
Dataset Title	RINA-CSM_ELLIPSO	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of ellipsometer at RINA-CSM partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date , layer thickness and associated model	
Responsible partner	RINA-CSM	
WP – Task	WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation	
Expected period	M4-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the thickness and optical properties (n&k) of layers of TCO layers developed in TERASUN	
F A I R	Findability	<p>Format: This dataset is stored in a spreadsheet (Excel file '.xlsx').</p> <p>Location: SharePoint folder</p> <p>Containing fields: non exhaustive list Layer types, sample name, date, equipment type, Thickness, n&k, number of points, methodology (using standard samples)</p> <p>Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP2_4_RINA-CSM_ELLIPSO_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Version numbering: not required as relying on SharePoint version tracking</p>
	Accessibility	<p>Access: Not openly available, publication possible</p> <p>Restrictions: this dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries through project intranet (Microsoft Teams).</p> <p>Justification of restriction (if so): the round robin may contain confidential information. Data is going to be used/presented in dissemination activities</p>
	Interoperability	<p>Data exchange and reuse ease:</p> <p>The data and methodologies will be exchange et reuse in the technical results of the project.</p>
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset through the project intranet. Access is granted via secure login to the designated Microsoft Teams platform without the need of a license. The data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WPs 3, 4 and 5.
Data security	The data collected for internal use in the project is not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after project. During project duration, there will be implemented the data security approaches presented in the DMP.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders	
Other comments	N/A	

FZU Datasets

<i>TERASUN_DS_WP2_FZU_Raman</i>		
Dataset Title	FZU_Raman	
Type of Data	Experimental	
Short description	The database contains the results of Raman spectroscopy measurement at FZU partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, Raman spectrum	
Responsible partner	FZU	
WP – Task	WP2 – Innovative texturization and nanophotonic structures WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules	
Expected period	M8-M36	
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals	To determine the thickness of thin silicon films and determining the light-trapping abilities of novel surfaces structures.	
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in the device format Location: FZU local storage Containing fields: Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP4_FZU_TEX Version numbering: date in format YYYY/MM/DD
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available. Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries granted access to FZU data storage. Justification of restriction (if so): Data will be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: Data will be provided in non-proprietary, widely adopted formats (CSV, txt, TIFF).
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset directly from the FZU storage. They will be granted access upon request. Data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WP 2.
Data security	Project-specific internal data are not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.	
Ethical aspects	EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders.	
Other comments	N/A	

<i>TERASUN_DS_WP3_FZU_PL</i>	
Dataset Title	FZU_PL
Type of Data	Experimental

Short description		The database contains the results of photoluminescence spectroscopy measurement at FZU partner site: process name or layer, sample name, date, PL spectrum
Responsible partner		FZU
WP – Task		WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period		M8-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To determine the thickness homogeneity of deposited thin silicon films and determining the passivation on novel surfaces structures.
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in the device format Location: FZU local storage Containing fields: Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP3_FZU_TEX Version numbering: date in format YYYY/MM/DD
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available. Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries granted access to FZU data storage. Justification of restriction (if so): Data will be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: Data are provided in non-proprietary, widely adopted formats (CSV, txt, TIFF).
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset directly from the FZU storage. They will be granted access upon request. Data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WP 3.
Data security		Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects		EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders.
Other comments		N/A

TERASUN_DS_WP4_FZU_Mod_AFM	
Dataset Title	FZU_AFM
Type of Data	Experimental
Short description	The database contains the results of topographical or electrical analysis (images): for textured wafers: pyramid counts on different points, pyramid size, homogeneous covering of films
Responsible partner	FZU

WP – Task		WP2 – T2.4 - Characterisation of wafer surface structure and nanophotonic structures on glass WP3- T3.6 - Characterisation of TCOs, metallisation, MOs and passivation WP4- T4.3 - Characterisation of cells and modules
Expected period		M8-M36
Purpose and relation with TERASUN goals		To determine the local inhomogeneity of deposited thin silicon films and determining the topography on novel surfaces structures.
F A I R	Findability	Format: This dataset is stored in the device format Location: FZU local storage Containing fields: Name convention followed: TERASUN_DS_WP4_FZU_Mod Version numbering: date in format YYYY/MM/DD
	Accessibility	Access: Not openly available. Restrictions: This dataset is not public. Available only to beneficiaries granted access to FZU data storage. Justification of restriction (if so): Data will be used/presented in dissemination activities.
	Interoperability	Data exchange and reuse ease: Data are provided in non-proprietary, widely adopted formats (CSV, txt, TIFF).
	Reusability	Project partners can access and utilise the dataset directly from the FZU storage. They will be granted access upon request. Data will be accessible throughout the project lifetime. Data will be used in WP 4.
Data security		Project-specific internal data is not intended for long-term storage. All personal information will be deleted upon project completion. Only essential, non-sensitive data may be retained.
Ethical aspects		EU data protection laws, including regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), govern personal data handling. These rules apply at international, European, and national levels, ensuring privacy rights across borders.
Other comments		N/A

Annex II: GDPR consent form

CONSENT FORM

IDENER as communication manager, produces a range of communications resources to TERASUN project. We like to share your names and pictures in our communications as it helps to demonstrate the difference our work is making. By completing this form, you give us permission to use your data in our communications for the next 3 years. Thank you for your help.

Full name	
Address	
Institution	
Phone	
Email	

What will my data be used for? (Please mark the options you are happy with, with an "X")

<input type="checkbox"/>	I agree that my data can be used <u>for all the points listed in this table below</u>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Presentations: TERASUN internal and external presentations	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Websites: TERASUN website and intranet	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Social media: TERASUN social media pages [<i>@TERASUN</i> , <i>LinkedIn: TERASUN project</i>]	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publications: TERASUN leaflets, posters, newsletters and other marketing materials	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Print and online media: National, regional and local papers; magazines and news sites	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Television and radio: National and regional television; national, regional and local radio	

Can I remain anonymous?

You can choose to have your real name published with your data or remain anonymous (under your institution name). Please tick one of the following options:

<input type="checkbox"/>	I am happy for my real name to be used	
<input type="checkbox"/>	I do not want my real name to be used	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Please tick this box if you do NOT want to be featured in imagery or video footage	

Are there any identifying features you do NOT want included in our communications work?

<input type="checkbox"/>	
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Please let us know if there are any ways in which you do NOT wish to be represented or described:

<input type="checkbox"/>	
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I am happy to give my permission

Please sign this form to show you are happy to give permission for your data to be used by TERASUN consortium for the purposes outlined above. Your story will not be used or stored for any longer than 3 years, unless you ask us to stop using it before then.

Location & date

Signature

Data protection: The information that you provide here will only be used to contact you about sharing your story in our communications work. We will not pass the details recorded on this form on to any other organisation without your permission. We will not store your data for any longer than 3 years.

Please return your completed form to Johannes Seif, Coordinator of the TERASUN project.
Thank you. If you have any questions about the form, please contact johannes.seif@idener.ai.

Changes

As mentioned in the executive summary, the changes have been highlighted with **yellow marker**. Major changes have been applied to:

- The TERASUN datasets have be updated (see yellow markings).
- The screenshot of the “Consent Form” has been updated to a version with higher resolution.
- The datasets provided by FZU have been added.